

ELSEVIER

Contents lists available at ScienceDirect

International Journal of Infectious Diseases

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/ijid

IJRadiation therapy for recurrent hydatid cyst of the pelvic bone: a case report

Marina Peña Huertas^{a,b,*}, Juan Zafra Martín^{c,d}, Ignacio Álvarez García de Quesada^e, Ana Aurora Díaz Gavela^{a,b,f}, Luis Leonardo Guerrero Gómez^f, Sofía Sánchez García^f, Eduardo Pardo Pérez^g, Felipe Couñago^{b,f}, Elia del Cerro Peñalver^{a,b,f}

^a Department of Radiation Oncology, Hospital Universitario Quirónsalud Madrid, 28223, Madrid, Spain

^b Medicine Department, School of Biomedical Sciences, Universidad Europea, 28670, Madrid, Spain

^c Department of Radiation Oncology, Hospital Universitario Virgen de la Victoria, 29010, Málaga, Spain

^d Cancer Molecular Biology Group, Section of Immuno-Oncology, Medical Research Center (CIMES), University of Malaga (UMA), Institute of Biomedical Research in Malaga (IBIMA), 29010, Málaga, Spain

^e Department of Orthopedic Surgery and Traumatology, Hospital Universitario Quirónsalud Madrid, 28223, Madrid, Spain

^f Department of Radiation Oncology, Hospital La Luz, 28003, Madrid, Spain

^g Department of Medical Physics and Radiological Protection, Hospital Universitario Quirónsalud Madrid, 28223, Madrid, Spain

ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received 3 November 2021

Revised 1 December 2021

Accepted 2 December 2021

KEYWORDS:

hydatidosis
bone disease
treatment
radiotherapy
surgery

ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND: Hydatid disease usually affects the liver, but can also extend to other locations, such as the bones. In these cases, complete resection of the bone is considered the only curative approach. However, this is rarely feasible, and patients are left with benzimidazoles as their only option. In this context, there is an evident need for alternative treatments that can improve results. We present the case of a patient with a treatment-refractory hydatid cyst of the bone, who successfully underwent radiotherapy (RT).

CASE SUMMARY: A 64-year-old woman was diagnosed with a hydatid cyst of the bone in the sacroiliac joint that caused her sciatalgia and paresthesia. She underwent treatment with albendazole and surgery, and was treated with further doses of albendazole after relapsing six months later. After 2 years, she required a new resection, achieving a stable disease for 2 more years. At this point, she began to suffer from more intense pain (visual analogue scale 6/10). Given that further surgery was no longer feasible, she underwent radiotherapy (54 Gy in 27 fractions). No treatment-related toxicity was observed. At 1 month after radiotherapy, the pain had completely disappeared; 9 months later, the patient remains asymptomatic. The titer of anti-*Echinococcus-granulosus* antibodies and the absolute volume of eosinophils decreased after treatment with radiotherapy. The cyst remains radiologically stable.

CONCLUSION: Although further studies are needed, radiotherapy seems to be effective for hydatid cysts that are refractory to other treatments.

© 2021 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd on behalf of International Society for Infectious Diseases. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

INTRODUCTION

Hydatidosis is a parasitic zoonosis caused by larvae of the *Echinococcus* tapeworm. Although it can affect almost any organ, the involvement of bone tissue is considerably rare (0.5–4%) (Liang et al., 2014; Manenti et al., 2020; Song et al., 2007). This bone disease usually appears in the form of pelvic hydatid cysts, representing around 28% of cases (Horton, 1989; Zlitni MD et al., 2001). While the disease can stay dormant for years, symptoms

tend to develop over time and can severely impact quality of life; these include local pain, pathological fractures, and even neural deficit (Song et al., 2007; Zlitni et al., 2001).

The management of bone disease is not simple, because it is usually diagnosed at an advanced stage. The traditional approach consists of surgery and systemic treatment with benzimidazoles (Horton et al., 1989; Song et al., 2007). For surgery to be effective, a complete resection of the disease must be performed. However, this can be challenging because the disease may destroy bone tissue and invade the surrounding soft tissue (Pamir et al., 2002). Moreover, the location of the disease can lead to a very aggressive or mutilating procedure. Even with these therapeutic options, recurrence rates of up to 50% have been described in the literature

* **Corresponding author:** Marina Peña Huertas, Department of Radiation Oncology, Hospital Universitario Quirónsalud Madrid, 28223, Madrid, Spain
E-mail address: marinapenuhuertas@gmail.com (M. Peña Huertas).

Figure 1. MRI of the cyst and perilesional bone edema: (left) prior to radiotherapy; (right) 9 months after treatment, showing where the areas of bone edema have decreased with stability of the cyst.

(Neumayr et al., 2013). This warrants the development of more effective treatment alternatives, such as radiotherapy (RT). Although the evidence remains scarce, RT has shown promising results in terms of controlling both symptoms and disease (Liang et al., 2014; Liang et al., 2019; Neumayr, 2015; Roiz, 1953; Ulger et al., 2013; Xie et al., 2015).

We introduce the case of a patient with a hydatid cyst of the bone in the sacroiliac joint who presented disease recurrence despite undergoing surgery on two occasions and receiving albendazole, and who was treated effectively with radiotherapy.

CASE REPORT

A 64-year-old woman was diagnosed in 2013 with a hydatid cyst of the bone in the left sacroiliac joint, following a history of pain and paresthesia in the left gluteus irradiating to the ipsilateral leg. She started treatment with albendazole 400 mg, twice a day, for 3 months, and surgical resection of the lesion was performed. Analysis of the surgical specimen revealed that the cyst was caused by an *E. granulosus*.

Six months after the intervention, she presented a local recurrence that was treated with albendazole for 1 year, achieving clinical stability. Two years later, clinical and radiological progression occurred; systemic treatment was restarted with a dose of 400 mg daily, and a new surgical resection was performed. The patient remained stable and asymptomatic for a further 2 years. However, she started to develop sacral pain and further radiological progression, and so the dose of albendazole was increased to 400 mg twice a day.

At this point, given the progression of the lesion and the previous procedures, a new surgery would have consisted of a hemipelvectomy, which would have been unacceptably aggressive for the patient. For this reason, it was decided to perform a treatment with RT as an alternative to surgery. When evaluated in the Department of Radiation Oncology, the patient presented sacral pain of 6 out of 10 on a visual analogue scale (VAS), which irradiated to the left leg.

In order to plan an adequate treatment volume, simulation PET-CT and pelvic MRI were performed, with both images fused to identify the cyst. These images showed a cystic lesion with an SUVmax of 9.2 and areas of perilesional bone edema. The cyst was contoured as our GTV, with areas of bone edema included in the CTV. The PTV consisted of a 7 mm margin from the CTV. PET-CT also served as a diagnostic tool for a solitary pulmonary nodule that was identified as a lung adenocarcinoma, and was treated with surgery and adjuvant chemotherapy.

A dose of 54 Gy was administered in 27 fractions (2 Gy/fraction) using volumetric arc radiotherapy (VMAT). This dose was defined after careful consideration of the proximity of the target volume to organs at risk, such as the sacral plexus and the rectum. The tolerance to the treatment was excellent, with no acute toxicity of any kind. Periodic serologies were performed to monitor the titer of anti-*Echinococcus-granulosus* antibodies, which went from 1/640 prior to RT to 1/160 9 months later. Moreover, the absolute volume of eosinophils decreased from $0.9 \times 10^3 \mu\text{l}$ to $0.1 \times 10^3 \mu\text{l}$. After 9 months of follow-up, the patient presented no pain (VAS 0/10), while MRI showed that the areas of bone edema had decreased and the cyst had stabilized (Figure 1).

DISCUSSION

As mentioned above, there is a need for alternative techniques and treatments in cases of recurring or inoperable hydatid cysts. Although evidence for the effectiveness of radiotherapy remains scarce, comprising mainly retrospective data, the technique has shown promising results in recent studies. For instance, the retrospective case series by Xie et al. (Xie et al., 2015) evaluated 40 patients treated with surgery ($n = 24$) or radiotherapy ($n = 16$). After treatment, 58.3% of patients in the surgery group reported local pain, compared with 18.8% in the RT group. Moreover, relapse occurred in 58.3% of patients who underwent surgery and in only 18.7% of those treated with RT. While these are interesting results, a review of the evidence in 2015 concluded that the available data do not warrant RT as a feasible treatment in cases where surgery can be performed safely (Neumayr, 2015). This paper, however, did suggest that RT could play a role as part of multimodal therapy, and in cases where surgery was not possible.

To avoid relapses after surgery, it has been suggested that resection margins should be wide (Liang et al., 2014; Zlitni et al., 2001). In our case, given the location of the lesion and invasion of bone structures, the margins were narrower than desired. This, in addition to the reported low efficacy of benzimidazoles (Manenti et al., 2020), could explain the recurrence in our patient.

In our case the patient had received multiple surgical treatments, and so the proposed intervention for the most recent relapse would have been extremely aggressive. Therefore, the patient was not willing to undergo surgery. In this context, after a thorough discussion with all the medical staff involved, it was decided to offer RT as an alternative.

As for the planning of RT, given the location of the disease and the previous surgeries, the aim was to prioritize safety and avoid a radiation-induced sacral plexopathy. Therefore, the treatment was administered using VMAT in order to achieve maximum precision

and dose conformation. In terms of fractionation, after a review of the literature, we opted for 54 Gy in 27 fractions, although doses up to 75 Gy have been reported (Xie et al., 2015). The treatment outcomes in our patient were excellent. After 9 months of follow-up, she remained asymptomatic with a radiologically stable disease. Although follow-up times remain short, and RT has not shown curative results in the literature, by delaying disease progression and controlling symptoms, the technique appears to have a relevant impact in these patients.

CONCLUSION

In cases of recurrent hydatid cysts of the bone with poor treatment options, radiotherapy seems to be a safe and effective alternative to mutilating surgery. Further studies are needed to evaluate this approach in a controlled setting and to better define the optimal fractionation and radiotherapy technique.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

All authors declare no conflicts of interest.

FUNDING SOURCE

There were no study sponsors for this manuscript.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

Ethical approval was not required.

REFERENCES

- Horton RJ. Chemotherapy of Echinococcus infection in man with albendazole. *Trans R Soc Trop Med Hyg* 1989;83(1):97–102.
- Liang Q, Wen H, Yunus A, Tian Z, Jiang F, Song X. Treatment experiences of pelvic bone hydatidosis. *Int J Infect Dis* 2014;18:57–61.
- Liang Q, Xiang H, Xu L, Wen H, Tian Z, Yunus A, et al. Treatment experiences of thoracic spinal hydatidosis: a single-center case-series study. *Int J Infect Dis* 2019;89:163–8.
- Manenti G, Censi M, Pizzicannella G, Pucci N, Pitocchi F, Calcagni A, et al. Vertebral hydatid cyst infection. A case report. *Radiol Case Rep* 2020;15(5):523–7.
- Neumayr A. Radiotherapy of osseous echinococcosis: where is the evidence? *Int J Infect Dis* 2015;33:75–8.
- Neumayr A, Tamarozzi F, Goblirsch S, Blum J, Brunetti E. Spinal cystic echinococcosis – a systematic analysis and review of the literature: Part 2. Treatment, follow-up and outcome. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis* 2013;7(9):e2458.
- Pamir MN, Ozduman K, Elmaci I. Spinal hydatid disease. *Spinal Cord* 2002;40(4):153–60.
- Roiz Noriega M. [Radiology and radiotherapy of echinococcosis, of bone]. *Rev Clin Esp* 1953;51(4):236–40.
- Song XH, Ding LW, Wen H. Bone hydatid disease. *Postgrad Med J* 2007;83(982):536–42.
- Ulger S, Barut H, Tunc M, Aydin E, Aydinkarahaliloğlu E, Gokcek A, et al. Radiation therapy for resistant sternal hydatid disease. *Strahlenther Onkol* 2013;189(6):508–9.
- Xie Z, Chen L, Xie Q, Bao Y, Luo X, Yi C, et al. Surgery or radiotherapy for the treatment of bone hydatid disease: a retrospective case series. *Int J Infect Dis* 2015;33:114–19.
- Zlitni MD M, Ezzaouia MD K, Lebib MD H, Karray MD M, Kooli MD M, Mestiri MD M. Hydatid cyst of bone: diagnosis and treatment. *World J Surg* 2001;25(1):75–82.